

Neural Network for Calibration of Electrical Models of Semiconductor Devices

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This paper presents the development of a neural network-based approach for the calibration of electrical models of semiconductor devices, focusing on diodes and MOSFET transistors. Extensive datasets from experimental measurements and simulations were utilized to train and validate the models. The calibrated models demonstrated high accuracy and performance across diverse operational conditions, proving the effectiveness of neural networks in automating the calibration process. This research advances the field of semiconductor modelling, with significant potential for application in optimizing device performance.

1. Introduction

The rapid advancement of semiconductor technology has produced increasingly intricate electrical models for devices such as diodes and MOSFET transistors. Accurate model calibration is crucial for improving device performance, but traditional methods usually fail to address the nonlinearities and complexities inherent in semiconductor behavior. Neural networks have developed in recent years as useful tools for solving these difficulties due to their capacity to simulate complicated interactions between input and output characteristics [1].

This paper discusses the calibration of electrical models for diodes and MOSFET transistors using neural networks, with comprehensive support from MATLAB simulations. The results demonstrate that neural network fitting aligns closely with the device characteristics, significantly enhancing the accuracy and performance of the models under varying operating conditions.

2. Model structure and simulation framework

This study utilizes neural network curve fitting to calibrate diode and MOSFET models. The neural network design for both semiconductor devices was implemented in MATLAB and focused on fitting the electrical model to observed data Fig. 1. Performance was measured in terms of accuracy and generalization.

For diodes, the neural network architecture consists of an input layer receiving the IV curves, followed by a hidden layer with non-linear processing, and an output layer predicting the forward current (I_f). For MOSFETs, the network takes gate voltage (V_G), drain-source voltage (V_d), and temperature (T) as inputs, utilizing a more intricate multi-layer architecture to capture the transistor's behaviour across various operating conditions. Both architectures were trained using a diverse dataset, ensuring accurate parameter extraction and robust generalization across different environments.

The neural network training database includes test and simulation data for diodes and MOSFETs, covering various temperatures, voltages, and currents. Key parameters for MOSFETs are gate voltage, drain-source voltage, and temperature, while diodes focus on forward voltage and current. Preprocessing, including logarithmic scaling and handling missing values [2], improved data consistency and enhanced the network's ability to generalize the complex relationships between input parameters and the devices' electrical characteristics [3].

Fig. 1. Neural network architecture for diode and transistor

3. Simulation result and discussion

The accuracy and functionality of the diode and MOSFET models were significantly enhanced using neural network curve fitting in MATLAB. The nonlinear characteristics of the diode were successfully captured by the neural network at several temperature ranges. The model's success is demonstrated in Fig. 2 by comparing the diode's projected and real currents. The measured data points (circles) and the red line, which represents the NNlogIf (logarithmic model), are nearly exactly aligned, especially in the lower current regions. This alignment shows how well the logarithmic model can predict the behaviour of diodes in situations where precise modelling is essential also , We used this model to analyse the diode in the forward region, but it can also be applied to the reverse region if needed, though our focus is on forward bias characteristics.

On the other hand, particularly in the lower current regions, the green line, which represents NNIf, does not match the measured data as well. This discrepancy suggests that the non-logarithmic model does worse at representing the behaviour of the diode at low currents. The discernible disparity highlights how important the logarithmic transformation is, as it significantly improves the model's capacity to forecast and calibrate the diode's characteristics. This kind of model improvement addresses the diode's nonlinear behaviour

more effectively and improves current prediction accuracy over a larger range of operating situations. This realization emphasizes the benefit of employing logarithmic scaling when working with electrical equipment that have a broad dynamic range.

For the MOSFET transistor, the calibration process was a series of patterns that determined the relationship between drain current, gate-to-source voltage and drain-to-source voltages across all temperatures. Fig. 3 is an illustration the output characteristics at 25°C, a very good agreement between the measured data (blue crosses) and the predicted data (green line), thus the neural network's accuracy in modelling the MOSFET's behaviour by the high temperature was verified. Fig. 4 demonstrates the output characteristics at 175°C which also demonstrates strong agreement between predictions and measured data, Fig. 5 shows the transfer characteristics for both temperature 25, 175 °C. The model's ability to handle different temperatures highlights its resilience and accuracy, making it highly valuable for practical MOSFET circuit design the case of one temperature across two temperatures [4].

Fig. 2. Result of curve fitting neural network for diode characteristic

Fig. 3. Output characteristics at 25°C

Fig. 4. Output characteristics at 175°C

Fig. 5. Transfer characteristics at temperatures 25 °C and 175 °C

4. Conclusion

This study was apparently successful in that it managed to focus on using neural networks to calibrate electrical models for diodes and MOSFET transistors. The neural networks were able to successfully show the non-linear characteristics of semiconductor devices under different working conditions by using the huge number of experimental and simulation data. The results showed that the model accuracy improved significantly while dealing with temperature, voltage, and current. This method provides an important vehicle for the semiconductor devices' performance enhancement, being able to outperform advanced circuit design.

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References

- [1] Butola, R., Li, Y. and Kola, S.R., *IEEE Open Journal of Nanotechnology*, 4, 181, 2023.
- [2] Boanta, Catalin & Brisan, C, *Sensors*, 22(21), 8356, 2022.
- [3] Kao, Ming-Yen & Kam, H. & hu, Chenming. *IEEE Electron Device Letters*. 43. 1-1. 2022.
- [4] Khakifirooz, Ali & Antoniadis, Dimitri, *IEEE Transactions on*. 56, 1674 ,1680.2009.